

EVENT DEFINITION FORM

Event: **Coagulation disorders:** venous thromboembolism, stroke, hemorrhagic disorders, CVST, thrombotic thrombocytopenia

Outcome/covariate: outcome

Version: **1.2**

Status: final

Contributing authors

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Miriam Sturkenboom	Final codes February run
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Miriam Sturkenboom	Separation of codes for different events 30-3-2021
Miriam Sturkenboom	Inclusion of codes used in final report ACCESS (20-08-2021)

1. Event definition

This event definition form is about multiple groups of diseases under the overarching name of: coagulation disorder. A coagulation disorder is a problem with blood clotting. This can either be too much clotting leading to thrombosis, emboli or stroke, or too little clotting leading to bleeding and again stroke.

The events that are in this EDF are:

- Deep vein thrombosis (DVT)
- Pulmonary embolus Together with DVT called venous thromboembolism
- Cerebrovascular stroke
- Limb ischemia Occlusion of an artery that supplies the limbs of blood.
- Haemorrhagic disease Bleeding disorders

Within this EDF we excluded perioperative, congenital or drug induced causes of a coagulation disorder.

Venous thromboembolism (VTE)

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) (1)

DVT refers to the formation of a blood clot in one of the body's large veins. Most of the time this formation happens in the lower limb. The blood clot is called a thrombus. This thrombus can block off a part or all of the blood flow. The result of this is that the leg will swell due to a higher pressure in the vein. The leg turns red and is painful.

The reason why DVT is a severe condition is because of the symptoms itself but mainly because of the high risk of developing a pulmonary thromboembolism (PE). PE happens in one third of DVT patients. PE has a high mortality rate.

Pulmonary thromboembolism (PE) (1)

When a thrombus, origination most often in the lower limb, breaks loose from the vessel wall it travels freely thru the blood vessel on its way to the heart and lungs until it hits a point where it can no longer pass. In PE the thrombus gets trapped in the long artery and closes off the blood supply to the part of the lung after the occlusion. This causes a drop in lung perfusion, a declining blood oxygen saturation, and sharp chest pain.

Stroke (2)

Acute stroke is defined as the acute onset of focal neurological findings in a vascular territory as a result of underlying cerebrovascular disease. This can happen in two ways. One is an ischemic stroke, where a small thrombus gets trapped in a blood vessel transporting blood to the brain. Ischemic stroke accounts for 85% of all acute strokes. The other 15% of stroke are haemorrhagic strokes which are caused by bursting of a blood vessel i.e. acute haemorrhage.

There are numerous causes of stroke, such as prolonged hypertension, arteriosclerosis, and emboli that have formed in the heart as a result of atrial fibrillation or rheumatic heart disease.

Limb ischemia (3)

Acute limb ischemia is defined as a quickly developing or sudden decrease in limb perfusion. Another word for limb ischemia is peripheral artery disease (PAD) or peripheral occlusive artery disease (POAD).

The decrease in perfusion is due to a occlusion of the artery leading to the leg or arm. Occlusion of the upper limb is very rare so we focus on the lower limbs.

The incidence of acute peripheral arterial occlusion causing acute lower extremity ischemia is approximately 1.5 cases per 10,000 persons per year. The clinical presentation depends upon the aetiology and whether the patient has underlying peripheral artery disease. Patients who present later than two weeks after the onset of the acute event are considered to have chronic lower extremity ischemia.

If a patient has symptoms of PAD, the ankle-brachial index (ABI) should be obtained. This is a measure for the severity of the PAD. A value <0.4 is indicative of severe ischemia.

Haemorrhagic disease (4)(5)(6)(7)

This part of the coagulation disorders focuses on a lack of blood clotting. The blood is hypocoagulable resulting in bleeding. The cause of this bleeding lays within a problem in haemostasis. Haemostasis consists of two parts, the primary and secondary haemostasis. The primary haemostasis consists of the production of an initial blood clot with thrombocytes sticking together. After this process, in the secondary haemostasis, this blood clot is secured with fibrin through a cascade of multiple coagulation factors.

Problems within the primary haemostasis result in excessive bleeding when a wound occurs. Whenever there is a problem within the secondary haemostasis, an initial blood clot if formed and the wound might be dry but the blood clot is weak and might break from time to time resulting in recurrent bleeding.

To focus on specific diseases to be able to get incidence rates about haemorrhagic diseases, we decided to focus on acquired thrombocytopenia for the primary haemostasis and acquired haemophilia for the secondary haemostasis. Haemophilia is the absence of coagulation factors necessary for making fibrin within a primary blood clot.

Acquired haemophilia occurs rarely with the incidence of approximately 1 to 4 per million/year, with severe bleeds in up to 90% of affected patients, and high mortality between 8-22%. Most often factor VIII is inhibited by neutralizing antibodies. This form is called acquired haemophilia A.

Thrombocytopenia can be caused in many different ways. For example, within pregnancy, by medication, as a result of a auto-immune reaction, due to infection, heavy alcohol consumption and some types of anaemia. In this situation of a possible connection between the corona vaccination and haemorrhagic disease we decided to excluded causes like: pregnancy, cancers, infections and inherited causes. The best representation for a possible vaccine induced thrombocytopenia is immune thrombocytopenia (ITP). Immune thrombocytopenia happens when your immune system mistakenly attacks and destroys platelets. This effect can be triggered after an infection.

Another distinction that is possible to make within haemorrhagic disease is between major, minor and trivial bleeding. Major bleeding is a haemorrhagic stroke or bleeding that requires transfusion, minor bleeding is any bleeding severe enough to disturb social activities, and trivial bleeding is no clinically unusual bleeding

Thrombotic thrombocytopenia syndrome

Based on the safety concerns for the adenovirus platforms we defined thrombocytopenia based on the draft definition of the Brighton Collaboration¹, which combines the criteria for thrombocytopenia and

¹ <https://brightoncollaboration.us/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/TTS-Interim-Case-Definition-v10.16.3-May-23-2021.pdf>

- Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) – symptoms will depend on the location of the thrombosis, for example: swelling, pain, redness, or warmth of an extremity; headache, visual disturbance, seizures for sinus vein thrombosis; abdominal pain for intraabdominal thrombosis
- Pulmonary thromboembolism (PE) - sudden onset shortness of breath, pleuritic chest pain, sudden death/pulseless electrical activity arrest [Wells criteria for scoring – based on clinical findings]
- Stroke
- Myocardial infarction
- Arterial thrombosis

In webinar organized by VAC4EU and based on the case series following AstraZeneca and J&J vaccine we decided that the occurrence of the diagnosis of thrombosis and thrombocytopenia should be within 10 days of each other.

2. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

VTE

deep vein thrombosis / pulmonary embolus

- Embolism
- Embolus
- Blood clot
- Infarction
- Occlusion

Pulmonary embolus

Synonyms for PE

- Lung infarction
- Blockage of the pulmonary artery
- Pulmonary thrombosis

Stroke

Synonyms for cerebrovascular stroke

- Stroke
- Cerebral stroke
- Acute stroke
- Apoplexy
 - o Cerebrovascular apoplexy
- Collapse
- Shock
- Attack
- Seizure (this is actually epilepsy)
- Fit
- Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA)
- Cerebrovascular accident (CVA)
- Brain vascular accident
- Brain infarction

Limb ischemia

Synonyms for limb ischemia

- Peripheral arterial disease (PAD)
- Peripheral occlusive arterial disease (POAD)
- Intermittent claudication
- Limb infarction

Haemorrhagic disease

Synonyms for haemorrhagic disease:

- excessive bleeding
- haemophilia
- bleeding disorder
- bleeding problem
- spontaneous bleeding
- haemorrhaging
- haemorrhagic disease
- haemorrhagic disorder
- coagulopathy
- coagulation disorder

3. Laboratory tests that are specific for event

Venous thromboembolism (8)(9)

DVT To make the diagnosis of DVT more likely it is possible to determine the D-dimer in blood. D-dimer is a substance that is released when a clot breaks down. A high D-dimer is suspicious for a DVT.

PE Laboratory tests are not diagnostic but alter the clinical suspicion for PE, confirm the presence of alternative diagnoses, and provide prognostic information in the event that PE is diagnosed:

- Complete blood count and serum chemistries Routine laboratory findings include leucocytosis, increased erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), and elevated serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST).
- Arterial blood gas (ABG) Unexplained hypoxemia in the setting of a normal chest radiograph should raise the clinical suspicion for PE and prompt further evaluation.
- Brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) Elevated BNP has limited diagnostic value in patients suspected of having PE. However, elevated BNP or its precursor, N-terminal (NT)-proBNP may be useful for prognostic risk stratification of patients diagnosed with acute PE.
- Troponin Similarly, serum troponin I and T levels are useful prognostically but not diagnostically
- D-dimer An elevated D-dimer alone is insufficient to make a diagnosis of PE, but a normal D-dimer can be used to rule out PE in patients with a low or intermediate probability of PE.

Stroke (10)(11)

A number of blood tests may be indicated in select patients with brain ischemia or haemorrhage, including:

- Blood glucose
- Complete blood count including haemoglobin, haematocrit, white blood cell count, and platelet count
- Prothrombin time, international normalized ratio (INR), and activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT)
- Thrombin time and/or ecarin clotting time if patient is known or suspected to be taking a direct thrombin inhibitor or a direct factor Xa inhibitor
- Blood lipids including total, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, and triglycerides.
- Toxicology screen to detect cocaine and other sympathomimetic drugs

Limb ischemia (3)

There no laboratory testing specific for limb ischemia.

Haemorrhagic disease(12)

General

- Complete blood count including: platelet count and morphology, fibrinogen level
- Genetic testing Genetic testing for known platelet function disorders in certain individuals with a suspected platelet disorder of genetic origin.

Secondary hemostasis

- PT and aPTT The international normalized ratio (INR) is used to normalize the PT result across all testing laboratories.
- Thrombin time and reptilase time The thrombin time (TT) and reptilase time (RT) both measure the final step in the clotting cascade (cleavage of fibrinogen to fibrin).
- Specific clotting factor assays e.g. Factor VIII

Primary haemostasis

- Von Willebrand disease (vWD) This includes von Willebrand factor (vWF) antigen, tests for vWF function, and factor VIII activity.
- Platelet function The platelet count and platelet morphology should be reviewed from the complete blood count (CBC). Additional testing can be done using platelet aggregation studies or the platelet function analyser (PFA-100)

4. Diagnostic tests that are specific for event

Venous thromboembolism (13)(9)

DVT The indications to anticoagulate are based upon a definitive diagnosis of DVT, usually made on compressive ultrasound (CUS) of the lower extremities.

- **Lower-extremity compressive ultrasound (CUS) with Doppler** Any obstruction in the veins of the leg can be made visible. A new case of DVT in the setting of symptoms consistent with PE is highly suggestive for PE, although not definitively diagnostic.

PE Pulmonary embolism is most often diagnosed through CTPA.

- **Electrocardiography (ECG)** abnormalities, although common in patients with suspected PE, are nonspecific.
- **Computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CTPA)** For most patients with suspected PE, CTPA is the first-choice diagnostic imaging modality because it is sensitive and specific for the diagnosis of PE, especially when incorporated into diagnostic algorithms, and alternate diagnoses may be discovered using this modality. When imaging is indicated and CTPA cannot be performed or is inconclusive V/Q scanning is recommend.
- **Ventilation perfusion scan (V/Q scan)** V/Q scanning is mostly reserved for patients in whom CTPA is contraindicated or inconclusive, or when additional testing is needed. A normal chest radiograph is usually required prior to V/Q scanning.
- **Chest radiograph** Nonspecific abnormalities on chest radiography are in PE, but a normal chest radiograph can be seen in 12 to 22% of patients. A chest radiograph is typically performed in most patients suspected of PE to look for an alternative cause of the patient's symptoms.

Stroke (10)

- **Noncontrast computed tomography (CT)** typically the first diagnostic study in patients with suspected stroke.
- **MRI**; the use of susceptibility sequences improves the sensitivity of MRI for early detection of haemorrhage.

MRI is more sensitive than CT for the early diagnosis of brain infarction.

Limb ischemia(3)

A diagnosis of acute extremity ischemia can generally be made based upon the history and physical examination, including assessment of the ankle-brachial index bilaterally.

- **ankle-brachial index bilaterally (ABI)** Comparison of the blood pressure measured at the ankle with the blood pressure measured at the arm. A low ankle-brachial index number can indicate narrowing or blockage of the arteries in the legs. A value <0.4 is indicative of severe ischemia.
- **Imaging (CTA)** Patients with viable or marginally threatened limbs are usually candidates for urgent vascular imaging. This is typically CT angiography (CTA), or catheter-based arteriography. CT angiography can reliably diagnose the location and severity of arterial stenosis or occlusion with high sensitivity and specificity, but does not offer a treatment option. Catheter-based arteriography does.

Haemorrhagic disease (14)

No diagnostic test is needed if the focus of the bleeding is visible.

- **CT imaging** in case of internal bleeding. To diagnose a intracerebral haemorrhage
- **Lumbar puncture** Spinal fluid might contain sign of bleeding.

5. Drugs that are used to treat event

Venous thromboembolism(13)(15)

Deep vein thrombosis Anticoagulation is the mainstay of therapy for patients with DVT. Initial anticoagulation:

- **Fondaparinux** (subcutaneous, low molecular weight (LMW) heparin)
- **Rivaroxaban, Apixaban, edoxaban** (oral, factor Xa inhibitors)
- **Unfractionated heparin (UFH)**
- **Dabigatran** (thrombin inhibitors)
- **Warfarin** (vitamin K antagonists)

For patients in whom outpatient therapy is selected, it is suggested to use LMW heparin overlapped with warfarin (dual therapy), pre-treatment with LMW heparin followed by the administration of either dabigatran or edoxaban (dual therapy), or anticoagulation with either rivaroxaban or apixaban.

PE treatment is a combination of respiratory and hemodynamic support and anticoagulation/thrombolysis.

- **Supplemental oxygen** should be administered to target an oxygen saturation ≥ 90 percent.
- **Intravenous fluid (IVF)** IVF is first-line therapy for patients with hypotension.
- **Vasopressors** Intravenous vasopressors are administered when adequate perfusion is not restored with IVF.
 - o Norepinephrine
 - o Dobutamine

The optimal vasopressor for patients with shock due to acute PE is unknown, but norepinephrine is generally preferred.

- **Empiric anticoagulation**
 - o LMW heparin may be chosen for patients with hemodynamically stable PE
 - o UFH is preferred by most experts in patients who are hemodynamically unstable in anticipation of a potential need for thrombolysis or embolectomy.
- **Thrombolysis** and/or catheter-based therapies may be considered on a case-by-case basis when the benefits are assessed by the clinician to outweigh the risk of haemorrhage.

Stroke (10)(16)

In case of a ischemic stroke:

- **Alteplase**, intravenous, improves outcomes in patients with acute ischemic stroke who can be treated within 3 to 4.5 hours from stroke onset.

In addition to intravenous thrombolysis with alteplase and endovascular thrombectomy, a number of interventions for ischemic stroke are associated with either reduced disability, complications, or stroke recurrence, including:

- **Aspirin** Antithrombotic therapy initiated within 48 hours of stroke onset
- **High intensity statins** Lipid lowering
- **Blood pressure reduction** after the acute phase of ischemic stroke has passed

Limb ischemia (17)

- **Aspirin** antithrombotic therapy
- **Statins** e.g. simvastatin
- **Beta-blockers** e.g. metoprolol

These drugs are critical to decrease perioperative cardiovascular complications in patients undergoing surgical vascular reconstruction.

Haemorrhagic disease (11)

Reversal of anticoagulation may be necessary in patients who suffer an intracranial haemorrhage (ICH) while taking warfarin. Anticoagulation is possible with:

- **Intravenous vitamin K,**
- **Four-factor prothrombin complex concentrate**
- **Fresh frozen plasma**
- **Protamine sulphate** recommended for urgent treatment of patients with heparin-associated ICH

Lowering blood pressure Useful intravenous agents for controlling blood pressure in this setting include:

- **Nicardipine, Clevidipine** (Dihydropyridine)
- **Labetalol, Esmolol** (Beta blocker)
- **Enalaprilat** (ACE-inhibitor)
- **Fenoldopam**
- **Phentolamine** (Alfa-blocker)

The choice of antihypertensive agent should account for the rapidity and extent of blood pressure reduction, method of delivery (bolus versus infusion), individual patient comorbidities, potential adverse effects, and local experience

Osmotic therapy

Mannitol Acute intracranial pressure elevation or life-threatening mass effect.

6. Procedures used specific for event treatment

Venous thromboembolism (13)(15)

DVT

- **Compression stockings:** Elastic graduated compression stockings are not routinely used in patients with DVT to prevent post-thrombotic syndrome (PTS)
- **Thrombolytic therapy and thrombectomy**
- **Inferior vena cava filter:** Typically, IVC filters are used in patients with acute proximal DVT and PE who have an absolute contraindication to anticoagulant therapy (e.g. recent surgery, haemorrhagic stroke, active bleeding)

PE

- **Inferior vena cava filter:** In patients with acute PE, the primary indication for IVC filter placement is when anticoagulation is contraindicated and when recurrent PE occurs despite therapeutic anticoagulation.
- **Embolectomy** Embolectomy is indicated in patients with hemodynamically unstable PE in whom thrombolytic therapy is contraindicated. It is also a therapeutic option in those who fail thrombolysis. Emboli can be removed surgically or using a catheter.
- **Surgical embolectomy:** The usual indication for surgical embolectomy is hemodynamic instability due to acute PE for patients in whom thrombolysis is contraindicated.

Stroke (16)(18)

Ischemic

- **Mechanical thrombectomy:** indicated for patients with acute ischemic stroke due to a large artery occlusion in the anterior circulation.

Haemorrhagic

- **Cerebrospinal fluid drainage:** Ventricular drainage of cerebrospinal fluid can help reduce elevated intracranial pressure.
- **Surgical removal of haemorrhage:** Cerebellar decompression should be performed as soon as possible for patients with cerebellar haemorrhage greater than 3 cm in diameter

Limb ischemia (19)

- **Balloon angioplasty:** Initial procedure for patients with an estimated life expectancy of two years or less, or those who do not have autogenous vein available as a conduit.
- **Bypass surgery:** For patients with an estimated life expectancy of more than two years, and who have available autogenous vein conduit.
- **Aortofemoral bypass graft:** In aorto-iliac occlusive disease in low-risk patients.
- **Endovascular grafts:** Endovascular stent grafts. Patency rates are inferior to conventional open reconstruction but they endovascular reconstruction affords a reasonable alternative.

Haemorrhagic disease (12)

Treatment is necessary in intracranial bleeding, see haemorrhagic stroke.

General bleeding disorders. Bleeding other than stroke.

- **Platelet transfusions** used in cases of thrombocytopenia or impaired platelet function
- **Admission of Fibrinogen or vitamin K**
- **Haemostatic products** Such as a prothrombin complex concentrate (PCC) or recombinant activated factor VII (rFVIIa) in a potentially fatal situation, these products may be administered.

7. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed

Venous thromboembolism (13)

DVT Can be either at the ER or in the outpatient setting. The decision to treat DVT in the outpatient setting should be made in the context of the patient's understanding of the risk-benefit ratio, preferences, and clinical condition.

PE Diagnosis at ER and later treatment in in-hospital setting.

Stroke

ER

Limb ischemia

ER

Haemorrhagic disease

ER or Outpatient specialist depending on the urgency of the bleeding.

8. Codes used in ACCESS

Venous thromboembolism

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	I26	pulmonary (acute) (artery)(vein) thromboembolism	C4290143	pulmonary (acute) (artery)(vein) thromboembolism	narrow
ICD10CM	I26	Pulmonary embolism	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
ICD10CM	I80	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
ICD10CM	I81	Portal vein thrombosis	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
ICD10CM	I82	Other venous embolism and thrombosis			narrow
ICD10CM	O08.2	Embolism following ectopic and molar pregnancy	C0495169	Embolism following abortion and ectopic and molar pregnancy	narrow
ICD10CM	O22.3	Deep phlebothrombosis in pregnancy	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
ICD10CM	O87.1	Deep phlebothrombosis in the puerperium	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
ICD9CM	451	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
ICD9CM	452	Portal vein thrombosis	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
ICD9CM	453				narrow
ICD9CM	415.1	Pulmonary artery embolism	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
ICD9CM	451.11	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of femoral vein (deep) (superficial)	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
ICD9CM	451.19	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of deep veins of lower extremities, other	C0155770	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other deep vessels of lower extremities	narrow
ICD9CM	451.8	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other sites	C0340692	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other sites	narrow
ICD9CM	451.9	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of unspecified site	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
ICD9CM	639.6	Embolism following abortion or ectopic and molar pregnancies	C0495169	Embolism following abortion and ectopic and molar pregnancy	narrow
ICD9CM	671.3	Deep phlebothrombosis, antepartum	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
ICD9CM	671.4	Deep phlebothrombosis, postpartum	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
ICD9CM	673.2	Obstetrical blood-clot embolism	C0157552	Obstetrical blood clot embolism	narrow
ICPC	K93	Pulmonary embolism	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
ICPC	K94	Phlebitis/thrombophlebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
ICPC2P	K93002	Embolism;pulmonary	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow

ICPC2P	K94003	Thrombosis;portal	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	G401.00	Pulmonary embolism			narrow
RCD2	G401.11	Infarction - pulmonary			narrow
RCD2	G401.12	Pulmonary embolus			narrow
RCD2	G401000	Post operative pulmonary embolus			narrow
RCD2	G402.00	Pulmonary infarct			narrow
RCD2	G80..	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
RCD2	G8016	Thrombophlebitis femoral vein	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
RCD2	G80z.	Phlebitis/thrombophlebitis NOS	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
RCD2	G81..	Portal vein thrombosis	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	G821.	Thrombophlebitis migrans	C0152250	Thrombophlebitis migrans	narrow
RCD2	G822.	Embolus/thrombosis-vena cava	C0155775	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava	narrow
RCD2	G822.00	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava			narrow
RCD2	G823.	Embolus/thrombosis-renal vein	C0155776	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein	narrow
RCD2	G823.00	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein			narrow
RCD2	G825.00	Thrombosis of subclavian vein			narrow
RCD2	G826.00	Thrombosis of internal jugular vein			narrow
RCD2	G82z100	Thrombosis of vein NOS			narrow
RCD2	Gyu80	[X]Phlb+thrbphlb/o dp vs/l ex	C0155770	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other deep vessels of lower extremities	narrow
RCD2	Gyu82	[X]Embolism+thrombosis/o spc vns	C0155777	Embolism and thrombosis of other specified veins	narrow
RCD2	L413.	Antenatal deep vein thrombosis	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	L4130	Antenatal DVT unspecified	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	L413z	Antenatal DVT NOS	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	L4140	Postnatal DVT unspecified	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
RCD2	L414z	Postnatal DVT NOS	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
RCD2	L432.	Obstetric blood-clot embolism	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
RCD2	L4320	Obst.blood-clot embol.unspec.	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
RCD2	L432z	Obst.blood-clot embolism NOS	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	1748006	tromboflebitis de la vena femoral profunda	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
SCTSPA	17920008	trombosis de la vena porta	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	31268005	tromboflebitis migratoria	C0152250	Thrombophlebitis migrans	narrow
SCTSPA	46253008	tromboflebitis de extremidades inferiores	C0265053	Thrombophlebitis of lower extremities	narrow
SCTSPA	49956009	trombosis de venas profundas preparto	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	56272000	flebotrombosis profunda postparto	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	59282003	embolia pulmonar	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	60601008	embolia obstétrica de coágulo de sangre	C0157552	Obstetrical blood clot embolism	narrow

SCTSPA	82385007	síndrome de Budd - Chiari	C0856761	Budd-Chiari Syndrome	narrow
SCTSPA	195394007	flebitis y tromboflebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SCTSPA	195410000	tromboflebitis de la vena femoral	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
SCTSPA	195431002	flebitis y tromboflebitis, SAI	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SCTSPA	195434005	flebitis y tromboflebitis, SAI	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SCTSPA	195437003	embolia y trombosis de la vena cava	C0155775	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava	narrow
SCTSPA	195438008	embolia y trombosis de la vena renal	C0155776	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein	narrow
SCTSPA	195627004	[X]flebitis y tromboflebitis de otros vasos profundos de las extremidades inferiores	C0155770	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other deep vessels of lower extremities	narrow
SCTSPA	195629001	[X]embolia y trombosis de otras venas especificadas	C0155777	Embolism and thrombosis of other specified veins	narrow
SCTSPA	200231004	trombosis venosa profunda prenatal, no especificada	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	200234007	trombosis venosa profunda prenatal, SAI	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	200236009	trombosis venosa profunda postnatal, no especificada	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	200239002	trombosis venosa profunda postnatal, SAI	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	200299000	embolia pulmonar por coágulo sanguíneo de origen obstétrico	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	200300008	embolia pulmonar de coágulo sanguíneo de causa obstétrica, no especificada	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	200305003	embolia pulmonar de coágulo sanguíneo de causa obstétrica, SAI	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	233935004	tromboembolia pulmonar	C0524702	Pulmonary Thromboembolisms	narrow
SCTSPA	233936003	embolia pulmonar masiva aguda	C0340535	Acute massive pulmonary embolism	narrow
SCTSPA	275517008	Superficial vein thrombosis (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	195418007	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of the leg NOS (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	46085004	Thrombosis of retinal vein (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	40107003	Phlebitis of lower extremities (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	40283005	Thrombophlebitis of superficial veins of lower extremity (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	1001000119102	Pulmonary embolism with pulmonary infarction (disorder)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1748006	Thrombophlebitis of deep femoral vein	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1748006	Thrombophlebitis of deep femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	7387004	Thrombophlebitis of tibial vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	14534009	Splenic vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16750002	Deep thrombophlebitis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	17513007	Thrombophlebitis of popliteal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	17920008	Portal vein thrombosis	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	18266009	Phlebothrombosis			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	31268005	Thrombophlebitis migrans	C0152250	Thrombophlebitis migrans	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	31268005	Thrombophlebitis migrans			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	31268005	Migratory thrombophlebitis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	31268005	Thrombophlebitis migrans			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	40198004	Thrombophlebitis of deep veins of lower extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	42861008	Thrombophlebitis of iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	46253008	Thrombophlebitis of lower extremities	C0265053	Thrombophlebitis of lower extremities	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	49956009	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	52496006	Thrombophlebitis of femoropopliteal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	56272000	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	58123006	Failed attempted termination of pregnancy with pulmonary embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	59282003	Pulmonary embolism	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	59282003	Pulmonary embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	59282003	Pulmonary embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	60601008	Obstetrical blood clot embolism	C0157552	Obstetrical blood clot embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	64662007	Pulmonary infarction			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	66877004	Phlegmasia cerulea dolens			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	74315008	Pulmonary microemboli			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	76598006	Penis vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	76598006	Penile venous thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	76598006	Penis vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Budd-Chiari syndrome	C0856761	Budd-Chiari Syndrome	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Budd - Chiari syndrome (hepatic vein thrombosis)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Budd Chiari syndrome			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Budd - Chiari syndrome (hepatic vein thrombosis)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Hepatic vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	82385007	Stuart-Brass syndrome			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	83727005	Hemorrhagic pulmonary infarction			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	95452006	Thrombophlebitis of deep veins of upper extremities			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	111293003	Venous thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	111293003	Venous thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	111293003	Thrombosis of vein NOS			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	128053003	Deep venous thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	128053003	Deep vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	128053003	Deep venous thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	128054009	Deep venous thrombosis of upper extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	128055005	Deep venous thrombosis of pelvic vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	128057002	Deep venous thrombosis of lower extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	134399007	Deep vein thrombosis of leg related to air travel			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155326007	Embolus - pulmonary	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155326007	(Pulmonary embolism) or (pulmonary infarct)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155454004	(Deep venous thrombosis of leg [& non-obstetric]) or (non-puerperal milk-leg) or (deep thrombophlebitis of leg)		narrow	
SNOMEDCT_US	155455003	Portal vein thrombosis	C0155773	Portal Vein Thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155456002	Thrombophlebitis migrans	C0152250	Thrombophlebitis migrans	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155458001	Thrombosis of vein NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155491005	Thrombophlebitis migrans	C0152250	Thrombophlebitis migrans	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	156268003	Antenatal deep vein thrombosis	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	156269006	Postnatal deep vein thrombosis	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	194882001	Pulmonary embolism	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	194882001	(Pulmonary embolus) or (pulmonary infarction)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	194883006	Postoperative pulmonary embolus			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195394007	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195403006	(Deep vein phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of the leg) or (deep vein thrombosis)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195410000	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	C0265066	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195410000	Thrombophlebitis of the femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195411001	Thrombophlebitis of the popliteal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195412008	Thrombophlebitis of the anterior tibial vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195414009	Thrombophlebitis of the posterior tibial vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195415005	Deep vein thrombophlebitis of the leg unspecified			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195419004	Thrombosis of vein of lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195425000	Thrombophlebitis of the common iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195426004	Thrombophlebitis of the internal iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195427008	Thrombophlebitis of the external iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195428003	Thrombophlebitis of the iliac vein unspecified			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	195429006	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of the iliac vein NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195431002	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis NOS	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195434005	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis NOS	C1367972	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195436007	Budd-Chiari syndrome	C0856761	Budd-Chiari Syndrome	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195437003	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava	C0155775	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195437003	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195437003	Embolism and thrombosis of the vena cava			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195438008	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein	C0155776	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195438008	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195438008	Embolism and thrombosis of the renal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195627004	[X]Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other deep vessels of lower extremities	C0155770	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of other deep vessels of lower extremities	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195629001	[X]Embolism and thrombosis of other specified veins	C0155777	Embolism and thrombosis of other specified veins	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	196998009	(Mesenteric thrombus &/or embolus) or (bowel: [infarction] or [gangrene]) or (acute intestinal vascular insufficiency) or (acute ischemic colitis &/or enteritis)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	197001004	Superior mesenteric vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	197003001	Mesenteric thrombus NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200231004	Antenatal deep vein thrombosis unspecified	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200234007	Antenatal deep vein thrombosis NOS	C0342044	Antepartum deep vein thrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200235008	DVT - deep venous thrombosis, postnatal	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200235008	DVT: [postnatal] or [obstetric phlegmasia alba dolens]			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200236009	Postnatal deep vein thrombosis unspecified	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200239002	Postnatal deep vein thrombosis NOS	C0342039	Postpartum deep phlebothrombosis	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200299000	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200300008	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism unspecified	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	200305003	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism NOS	C1279439	Obstetric blood-clot pulmonary embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	213220000	Postoperative deep vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233935004	Pulmonary thromboembolism	C0524702	Pulmonary Thromboembolisms	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233935004	Pulmonary thromboembolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233936003	Acute massive pulmonary embolism	C0340535	Acute massive pulmonary embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233937007	Subacute massive pulmonary embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233938002	Pulmonary fat embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	233939005	Subacute pulmonary fat embolism			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	233940007	Pulmonary tumor embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	234041004	Inferior mesenteric vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	234044007	Iliofemoral deep vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	234049002	Embolus of vein NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	266269008	Thrombosis of vein NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	266292008	Embolus - pulmonary	C0034065	Pulmonary Embolism	narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	266328001	(Deep venous thrombosis of leg [& non-obstetric]) or (non-puerperal milk-leg) or (deep thrombophlebitis of leg)			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	276494008	Phlebitis and/or thrombophlebitis of iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	280964006	Pulmonary air embolism			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	280966008	Phlegmasia alba dolens - obstetric			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	281595001	Thrombosis of inferior vena cava			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	297156001	Axillary vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	309735004	Thrombosis of vein of lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	312587007	Thrombophlebitis of iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	366830006	Deep vein thrombosis of leg related to air travel			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	366911007	Deep vein thrombosis of leg related to air travel			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	366912000	Deep vein thrombosis of lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	370248003	Deep venous thrombosis of leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	370249006	Thrombosis of vein of leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	371051005	Traumatic thrombosis of axillary vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	400047006	Peripheral vascular disease			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	404223003	Deep venous thrombosis of lower extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	413956008	Deep vein thrombosis of leg related to intravenous drug use			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	427775006	Deep venous thrombosis of profunda femoris vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	427776007	Thrombosis of the popliteal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	428781001	Deep venous thrombosis associated with coronary artery bypass graft			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	429098002	Other venous embolism and thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	429434005	Superficial vein thrombosis			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	438483005	Thrombophlebitis of subclavian vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	438646004	Thrombophlebitis of axillary vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	438647008	Thrombosis of subclavian vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	438647008	Thrombosis of subclavian vein			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	438785004	Deep venous thrombosis of tibial vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	441746000	Infarction of lung due to iatrogenic pulmonary embolism		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	443210003	Deep venous thrombosis of peroneal vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	444325005	Bilateral deep vein thrombosis of lower extremities		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	444816006	Embolism from thrombosis of vein of lower extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	703277001	Deep venous thrombosis of femoropopliteal vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	703636009	Pulmonary oil microembolism		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	706870000	Acute pulmonary embolism		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	707414004	Acute pulmonary thromboembolism		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	713078005	Pulmonary embolism on long-term anticoagulation therapy		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	723859005	Pulmonary embolism due to and following acute myocardial infarction		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	762256003	Thrombosis of iliac vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	840713005	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of iliac vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	860699005	Deep vein thrombosis of lower extremity due to intravenous drug use		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	651000119108	Acute deep vein thrombosis of lower limb		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1,001E+12	Pulmonary embolism with pulmonary infarction		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1001000119102	Pulmonary embolism with pulmonary infarction		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	5001000124101	Thrombosis of internal jugular vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132111000119107	Acute deep venous thrombosis of lower limb due to coronary artery bypass grafting		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132241000119103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of calf		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132251000119101	Acute deep venous thrombosis of popliteal vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132261000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of tibial vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132271000119105	Acute deep venous thrombosis of thigh		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132281000119108	Acute deep venous thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132291000119106	Acute deep venous thrombosis of femoral vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132301000119107	Acute deep venous thrombosis of iliofemoral vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132321000119103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of upper extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	132611000119104	Acute thrombosis of subclavian vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	133421000119101	Acute thrombosis of mesenteric vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	134961000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of axillary vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	135001000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of internal jugular vein		narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	136771000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of upper extremity as complication of procedure			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	136781000119101	Acute deep venous thrombosis of lower extremity as complication of procedure			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	143561000119108	Acute thrombosis of splenic vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	176351000000100	Deep vein thrombosis of leg related to intravenous drug use			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285261000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of both upper extremities			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285271000119105	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left upper extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285281000119108	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right upper extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285321000119103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral axillary veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285331000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left axillary vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285341000119109	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right axillary vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285381000119104	Bilateral acute deep vein thrombosis of femoral veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285391000119101	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285401000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285441000119102	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral iliofemoral veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285451000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of iliofemoral vein of left leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285461000119103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of iliofemoral vein of right lower extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285501000119103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral internal jugular veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285511000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left internal jugular vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285521000119107	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right internal jugular vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285561000119102	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral popliteal veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285571000119108	Acute deep venous thrombosis of popliteal vein of left leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285581000119106	Acute deep venous thrombosis of popliteal vein of right leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285621000119106	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral tibial veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285631000119109	Acute deep venous thrombosis of tibial vein of left leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	285641000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of tibial vein of right leg			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	286411000119108	Acute bilateral thrombosis of subclavian veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	286421000119101	Acute thrombosis of left subclavian vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	286431000119103	Acute thrombosis of right subclavian vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	293471000119106	Acute deep vein thrombosis of bilateral iliac veins			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	293481000119109	Acute deep vein thrombosis of right iliac vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	293491000119107	Acute deep vein thrombosis of left iliac vein			narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	328511000119109	Saddle embolus of pulmonary artery		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	350291000119100	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral legs		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	350301000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left lower extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	350311000119101	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right lower extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	432201000124103	Infarction of lung due to embolus		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	448831000124105	Deep venous thrombosis of right lower extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	448841000124100	Deep venous thrombosis of left lower extremity		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	449691000124103	Acute deep venous thrombosis of upper extremity after coronary artery bypass graft		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	503701000000105	Deep vein thrombosis of peroneal vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	509701000000108	Deep venous thrombosis of peroneal vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	587741000000103	Deep vein thrombophlebitis of the leg unspecified		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	587791000000108	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of the iliac vein NOS		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	850901000000106	Thrombosis of subclavian vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	850911000000108	Thrombosis of subclavian vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	864191000000104	Thrombosis of internal jugular vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	864201000000102	Internal jugular vein thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	864211000000100	Thrombosis of external jugular vein		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	978421000000101	Unprovoked deep vein thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	978431000000104	Unprovoked deep vein thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	978441000000108	Provoked deep vein thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	978451000000106	Provoked deep vein thrombosis		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	12237551000119104	Acute deep venous thrombosis of bilateral calves		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	12237631000119109	Acute deep venous thrombosis of left calf		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	12237711000119106	Acute deep venous thrombosis of right calf		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15708201000119101	Acute deep vein thrombosis of right upper limb following procedure		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15708281000119109	Acute deep vein thrombosis of right upper limb following coronary artery bypass graft		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15708401000119100	Acute deep vein thrombosis of left upper limb following procedure		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15708441000119103	Acute deep vein thrombosis of left upper limb following coronary artery bypass graft		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15711241000119106	Acute deep vein thrombosis of right lower limb following procedure		narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15711361000119101	Acute deep vein thrombosis of bilateral lower limbs following coronary artery bypass graft		narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	15711401000119105	Acute deep vein thrombosis of left lower limb following procedure			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	15964701000119109	Saddle embolus of pulmonary artery with acute cor pulmonale			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16006271000119105	Thrombophlebitis of deep vein of left upper limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16006311000119105	Thrombophlebitis of deep vein of right upper limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16011991000119109	Thrombophlebitis of right femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16012071000119101	Thrombophlebitis of left femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16012111000119108	Thrombophlebitis of right deep femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16012151000119109	Thrombophlebitis of left deep femoral vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16014351000119101	Thrombophlebitis of deep vein of left lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16014391000119106	Thrombophlebitis of deep vein of bilateral lower limbs			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16014431000119101	Thrombophlebitis of deep vein of right lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	16730001000004104	Thrombosis of left peroneal vein			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	20850001000004108	Deep venous thrombosis of right upper extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	25820001000004100	Deep venous thrombosis of left upper extremity			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	95446005	Mesenteric thrombus NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	95446006	Mesenteric thrombus NOS			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	404223003	Deep vein thrombosis of lower limb			narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	234043001	Thrombosis of vein of leg			narrow

Ischemic stroke

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	G45.9	Transient cerebral ischemic attack, unspecified	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
ICD10CM	I63	Cerebral infarction	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
ICD10CM	I63.9	Cerebral infarction, unspecified	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
ICD10CM	I63.9	Stroke NOS	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
ICD10CM	I63.9	Cerebral infarction, unspecified	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
ICD9CM	434	Occlusion of cerebral arteries	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
ICD9CM	435	TIA	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
ICPC	K90.03	Stroke/cerebrovasc accident	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
ICPC	K89	TIA			possible
RCD2	G66..	Stroke/CVA unspecified	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
RCD2..	G64..	Cerebral infarction			narrow

SCTSPA	20059004	oclusión de arteria cerebral	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SCTSPA	38609002	accidente isquémico transitorio	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SCTSPA	82797006	accidente cerebrovascular	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SCTSPA	155403004	Cerebral artery occlusion NOS	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SCTSPA	195207009	isquemia cerebral transitoria, SAI	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SCTSPA	230690007	accidente cerebrovascular	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SCTSPA	195185009	Cerebral infarct due to thrombosis of precerebral arteries			narrow
SCTSPA	125081000119106	Cerebral infarction due to occlusion of precerebral artery			narrow
SCTSPA	195186005	Cerebral infarction due to embolism of precerebral arteries			narrow
SCTSPA	230692004	infarto - precerebral	C0393952	Infarction - precerebral	narrow
SCTSPA	266255008	oclusión de arteria cerebral	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SCTSPA	266256009	infarto cerebral, SAI	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SCTSPA	266256009	infarto cerebral, SAI	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SCTSPA	266257000	ataque isquémico transitorio	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SCTSPA	270883006	accidente cerebrovascular, no especificado	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SCTSPA	286956007	oclusión de arteria cerebral, SAI	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SCTSPA	313242003	ataques isquémicos transitorios	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SCTSPA	313267000	accidente cerebrovascular, SAI	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SCTSPA	371041009	accidente cerebrovascular por embolia	C0262469	Embolic stroke	narrow
SCTSPA	373606000	accidente cerebrovascular oclusivo	C1298680	Occlusive stroke	narrow
SCTSPA	422504002	accidente cerebrovascular isquémico	C0948008	Ischemic stroke	narrow
SCTSPA	432504007	infarto cerebral	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SCTSPA	725132001	accidente cerebrovascular isquémico sin déficit residual	C3648410	Ischemic stroke without residual deficits	narrow
SCTSPA	266257000	Transient ischemic attack (disorder)			Possible
SCTSPA	432504007	Cerebral infarction (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	371040005	Thrombotic stroke (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	230698000	Lacunar infarction (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	422504002	Ischemic stroke (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	9901000119100	Occlusion of cerebral artery with stroke (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	230717002	Vertebrobasilar territory transient ischemic attack (disorder)			Possible
SCTSPA	371041009	Embolic stroke (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	427296003	Thalamic infarction (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	413758000	Cardioembolic stroke (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	266254007	Carotid artery occlusion (disorder)			Possible
SCTSPA	230692004	Infarction - precerebral (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	266253001	Precerebral arterial occlusion (disorder)			Possible
SNOMED CT_US	20059004	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow

SNOMED CT_US	20059004	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	20059004	Cerebral artery occlusion	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	38609002	Temporary cerebral vascular dysfunction	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	71444005	Cerebral thrombosis			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	75543006	Cerebral embolism			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	78569004	Inferior cerebellar artery syndrome			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	78569004	Posterior inferior cerebellar artery syndrome			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	82797006	Apoplexy	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	95457000	Brainstem infarction NOS			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	95460007	Cerebellar infarction			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155388006	Cerebrovascular accident	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155400001	Cerebral arterial occlusion	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155403004	Cerebral artery occlusion NOS	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155404005	Transient cerebral ischaemia	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	155405006	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155405006	Accident - cerebrovascular	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	155405006	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195179002	Infarction - precerebral	C0393952	Infarction - precerebral	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195188006	Cerebral infarction	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195188006	Cerebral infarction	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195188006	Cerebral arterial occlusion	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195189003	Cerebral infarction due to thrombosis of cerebral arteries			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195190007	Cerebral infarction due to embolism of cerebral arteries			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195191006	Cerebral infarction NOS	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195196001	Transient cerebral ischaemia	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	195207009	Transient cerebral ischaemia NOS	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	195208004	CVA - Cerebrovascular accident unspecified	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195212005	Brain stem stroke syndrome			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195213000	Cerebellar stroke syndrome			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195216008	Left sided CVA			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195217004	Right sided CVA			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	230690007	Cerebrovascular accident	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow

SNOMED CT_US	230690007	Stroke and cerebrovascular accident unspecified			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195185009	Cerebral infarct due to thrombosis of precerebral arteries			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	125081000119106	Cerebral infarction due to occlusion of precerebral artery			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195186005	Cerebral infarction due to embolism of precerebral arteries			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	230691006	CVA - cerebral artery occlusion			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	230692004	Infarction - precerebral	C0393952	Infarction - precerebral	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	230698000	Lacunar stroke	C3178801	Stroke, Lacunar	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266255008	Cerebral arterial occlusion	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266256009	Cerebral infarction NOS	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266256009	Cerebral infarction NOS	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266257000	Transient cerebral ischemia	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	266312006	Cerebrovascular accident	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266314007	Transient cerebral ischaemia	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	266315008	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266315008	Accident - cerebrovascular	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	266315008	Cerebral infarct	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	270883006	Stroke and cerebrovascular accident unspecified	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	286956007	Cerebral artery occlusion NOS	C0028790	Cerebral artery occlusion	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	307766002	Left sided cerebral infarction			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	307767006	Right sided cerebral infarction			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	313242003	Transient ischaemic attacks	C0007787	Transient Ischemic Attack	possible
SNOMED CT_US	313267000	Stroke NOS	C0038454	Cerebrovascular accident	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	371041009	Embolic stroke	C0262469	Embolic stroke	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	373606000	Occlusive stroke	C1298680	Occlusive stroke	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	413102000	Infarction of basal ganglia			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	422504002	Ischemic stroke	C0948008	Ischemic stroke	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	432504007	Cerebral infarction	C0007785	Cerebral Infarction	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	725132001	Ischemic stroke without residual deficits	C3648410	Ischemic stroke without residual deficits	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	457551000124104	Acute stroke	C0751956	Acute Cerebrovascular Accidents	narrow

Cerebral Venous Sinus thrombosis

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	G08	Intracranial and intraspinal phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	C0494450	Intracranial and intraspinal phlebitis and thrombophlebitis	Narrow
ICD10CM	I67.6	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of cerebral vein	C2882442	cerebral vein thrombosis nonpyogenic	narrow
ICD9CM	325	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of intracranial venous sinuses	C0154662	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of intracranial venous sinuses	Narrow
ICD9CM	437.6	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	C0155731	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	Narrow
RCD2	F050.	Embolism CNS venous sinus	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
RCD2	F0500	Embolism cavernous sinus	C0340727	Embolism cavernous sinus	possible
RCD2	F0503	Embolism transverse sinus	C0270645	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	possible
RCD2	F050z	Embolism CNS venous sinus NOS	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
RCD2	F0510	Thrombosis cavernous sinus	C0238454	Cavernous Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	F0512	Thrombosis lateral sinus	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	F0513	Thrombosis transverse sinus	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
RCD2	F0532	Thrombophlebitis lat. sinus	C0751827	Lateral Sinus Thrombophlebitis	narrow
RCD2	G676000	Cerebral infarction due to cerebral venous thrombosis, nonpyogenic			narrow
RCD2	G6W..00	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of precerebral arteries			narrow
SCTSPA	14246007	embolia de seno venoso intracraneal	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	21258007	trombosis de seno venoso lateral	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	23819000	embolia de seno cavernoso venoso	C0270644	Embolism of cavernous venous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	42970005	trombosis no piógena de seno venoso intracraneal	C0155731	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	narrow
SCTSPA	78682001	tromboflebitis del seno venoso lateral	C0751827	Lateral Sinus Thrombophlebitis	narrow
SCTSPA	80758005	embolia de seno venoso lateral	C0270645	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	89980009	trombosis de seno venoso cavernoso	C0238454	Cavernous Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	95455008	trombosis de las venas cerebrales	C0151945	Thrombosis of cerebral veins	narrow
SCTSPA	95461006	tromboflebitis de vena cerebral	C0235502	Thrombophlebitis of cerebral vein	narrow
SCTSPA	123269000	trombosis no piogénica de seno venoso intracraneal - RETIRADO -	C0155731	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	narrow
SCTSPA	192754003	embolia de seno cavernoso	C0340727	Embolism cavernous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	192757005	embolia de seno transverso	C0270645	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	192758000	embolia de seno venoso del sistema nervioso central, SAI	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
SCTSPA	192761004	trombosis de seno transverso	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SCTSPA	192772009	tromboflebitis de seno lateral	C0751827	Lateral Sinus Thrombophlebitis	narrow
SCTSPA	230722002	trombosis venosa cerebral de vena cortical	C0338580	Cerebral venous thrombosis of cortical vein	narrow
SCTSPA	15742000	Thrombosis of inferior sagittal sinus (disorder)			narrow

SCTSPA	18058007	Phlebitis of intracranial venous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	192753009	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis of intracranial sinuses (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	192760003	Thrombosis of superior longitudinal sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	192770001	Thrombophlebitis of cavernous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	192771002	Thrombophlebitis of superior longitudinal venous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	230720005	Cerebral venous thrombosis of straight sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	230721009	Cerebral venous thrombosis of sigmoid sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	297157005	Intracranial venous thrombosis (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	3168002	Thrombophlebitis of intracranial venous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	70607008	Thrombosis of superior sagittal sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	72094000	Thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SCTSPA	195230003	Cerebral infarction due to cerebral venous thrombosis, non-pyogenic			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	14246007	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	21258007	Thrombosis of lateral venous sinus	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	23819000	Embolism of cavernous venous sinus	C0270644	Embolism of cavernous venous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	42970005	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	C0155731	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	78682001	Thrombophlebitis of lateral venous sinus	C0751827	Lateral Sinus Thrombophlebitis	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	80758005	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	C0270645	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	89980009	Thrombosis of cavernous venous sinus	C0238454	Cavernous Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	95455008	Thrombosis of cerebral veins	C0151945	Thrombosis of cerebral veins	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	95461006	Thrombophlebitis of cerebral vein	C0235502	Thrombophlebitis of cerebral vein	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	123269000	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	C0155731	Nonpyogenic thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	192754003	Embolism cavernous sinus	C0340727	Embolism cavernous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	192757005	Embolism transverse sinus	C0270645	Embolism of lateral venous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	192758000	Embolism central nervous system venous sinus NOS	C0340731	Embolism of intracranial venous sinus	possible
SNOMED CT_US	192759008	Thrombosis of intracranial venous sinus			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	192761004	Thrombosis transverse sinus	C0270639	Lateral Sinus Thrombosis	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	192772009	Thrombophlebitis lateral venous sinus	C0751827	Lateral Sinus Thrombophlebitis	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	230722002	Cerebral venous thrombosis of cortical vein	C0338580	Cerebral venous thrombosis of cortical vein	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	5491000124101	Thrombophlebitis of transverse sinus	C3266647	Thrombophlebitis of transverse sinus	narrow
SNOMED CT_US	192771002	Thrombophlebitis of superior longitudinal venous sinus (disorder)			narrow
SNOMED CT_US	195230003	Cerebral infarction due to cerebral venous thrombosis, non-pyogenic			narrow

SNOMED CT_US	192760003	Thrombosis of superior longitudinal sinus (disorder)			narrow
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Hemorrhagic stroke (excluding subarachnoid)

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	I61	Deep intracerebral hemorrhage (nontraumatic)	C2882317	Deep intracerebral hemorrhage (nontraumatic)	Narrow
ICD10CM	I62	other intracranial hemorrhage			Narrow
ICD9CM	431	Intracerebral hemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
ICPC	K90.02	Hem stroke			Narrow
ICPC2P	K90006	Haemorrhage;cerebral	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
ICPC2P	K90013	Rupture;blood vessel;brain	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
RCD2	G61z.	Intracerebral haemorrhage NOS	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
RCD2	G62..	Other and unspecified intracranial haemorrhage			Narrow
SCTSPA	1508000	hematoma intracerebral	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SCTSPA	155394003	Cerebral haemorrhage NOS	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SCTSPA	195173001	hemorragia intracerebral, SAI	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SCTSPA	266313001	hemorragia cerebral, SAI	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SCTSPA	274100004	hemorragia cerebral	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SCTSPA	21454007	Subarachnoid hemorrhage (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	449020009	Intraparenchymal hemorrhage of brain (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	262955000	Traumatic intracranial subarachnoid hemorrhage (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	270907008	Spontaneous subarachnoid hemorrhage (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	82999001	Epidural hemorrhage (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	431266005	Intraparenchymal hematoma of brain (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	301765007	Cerebellar hematoma (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	269145001	Traumatic intracranial hemorrhage (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	450425005	Intracranial hematoma (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	301764006	Hematoma of brain (disorder)			Narrow
SCTSPA	450418003	Cerebral hemorrhage following injury (disorder)			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1386000	Intracranial haemorrhage NOS			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	1508000	Cerebral parenchymal haemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	7713009	Pontine haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	28293008	Hereditary factor VIII deficiency disease			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	35486000	Subdural haemorrhage NOS			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	41788008	Hereditary factor IX deficiency disease			Narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	49422009	Cortical haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	52201006	Internal capsule haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	75038005	Cerebellar haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155389003	Cerebral haemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155391006	Cerebral parenchymal haemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155394003	Cerebral haemorrhage NOS	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195163003	CVA - cerebrovascular accident due to intracerebral haemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195165005	Basal nucleus haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195167002	External capsule haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195168007	Intracerebral haemorrhage, intraventricular			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195169004	Intracerebral haemorrhage, multiple localized			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195173001	Intracerebral haemorrhage NOS	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195176009	Subdural haemorrhage - nontraumatic			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	230706003	Hemorrhagic cerebral infarction			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	230710000	Lobar cerebral haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	266313001	Cerebral haemorrhage NOS	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	267530009	Acute posthemorrhagic anemi			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	274100004	Cerebral hemorrhage	C2937358	Cerebral Hemorrhage	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	274100004	Intracerebral haemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	397809001	Nontraumatic epidural hemorrhage			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	732923001	Bulbar haemorrhage			Narrow

Disseminated intravascular coagulation

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	D65	Disseminated intravascular coagulation [defibrination syndrome]	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
ICD10CM	D65	Purpura fulminans	C0085650	Purpura Fulminans	Narrow
ICD10CM	P60	Disseminated intravascular coagulation of newborn	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
ICD9CM	286.6	Defibrination syndrome	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
ICD9CM	776.2	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
ICPC2P	B83017	Disseminated intravascular coag	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
RCD	D306.	Disseminated intravascular coagulation	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow

RCD	Q452.	Newborn disseminated intravascular coagulation	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
RCD	X20FR	Purpura fulminans	C0085650	Purpura Fulminans	Narrow
RCD2	D306.	Defibrination syndrome	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
RCD2	Q452.	Newborn dissem.intravasc.coag.	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
SCTSPA	13507004	púrpura fulminante	C0085650	Purpura Fulminans	Narrow
SCTSPA	34417008	coagulación intravascular diseminada en el recién nacido	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
SCTSPA	67406007	coagulación intravascular diseminada	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	13507004	Purpura fulminans	C0085650	Purpura Fulminans	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	34417008	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	C0158992	Disseminated intravascular coagulation in newborn	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	67406007	Disseminated intravascular coagulation	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	67406007	Disseminated intravascular coagulation			Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	267563002	Dissemin. intravascular coag.	C0012739	Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation	Narrow

Thrombotic microangiopathy

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Algorithm
ICD10CM	M31.1	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
ICD10CM	M31.1	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
ICD9CM	446.6	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
RCD2	G756.	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
RCD2	G756.	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
RCD2	G756z	Thrombotic microangiopathy NOS	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SCTSPA	78129009	púrpura trombocitopénica trombótica	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
SCTSPA	126729006	microangiopatía trombótica	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SCTSPA	195360005	microangiopatía trombótica, SAI	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SCTSPA	302873008	púrpura trombocitopénica	C0857305	Thrombocytopenic purpura	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	78129009	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	78129009	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	126729006	Thrombotic microangiopathy	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	154822006	Thrombocytopenic purpura	C0857305	Thrombocytopenic purpura	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	155443009	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	191315003	Thrombocytopenic purpura	C0857305	Thrombocytopenic purpura	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195358008	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow

SNOMEDCT_US	195359000	Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	195360005	Thrombotic microangiopathy NOS	C2717961	Thrombotic Microangiopathies	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	267564008	Thrombocytopenic purpura	C0857305	Thrombocytopenic purpura	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	360402008	Moschcowitz syndrome	C0034155	Purpura, Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic	Narrow

10. Algorithm

TTS:

- VTE plus thrombocytopenia
- Ischemic Stroke/CAD plus thrombocytopenia
- CVST plus thrombocytopenia
- VTE or Ischemic stroke or CAD or CVST plus thrombocytopenia

11. Background rates

Venous thromboembolism

We used the following search string:

Search: (((((((((((((((((((((((venous thromboembolism[MeSH Terms]) AND (incidence[Text Word])) NOT (surgery[Text Word])) NOT (malignancy[Text Word])) NOT (cancer[Text Word])) NOT (recurrent[Text Word])) NOT (in hospital[Text Word])) NOT (post discharge[Text Word])) NOT (COVID)) NOT (fracture[Text Word])) NOT (hospitalized[Text Word])) NOT (intensive care[Text Word])) NOT (pregnancy[Text Word])) NOT (pregnant[Text Word])) NOT (replacement[Text Word])) NOT (arthroplasty[Text Word])) NOT (treatment[Text Word])) AND (control[Text Word])) NOT (trauma[Text Word])) NOT (obese[Text Word])) NOT (immobilized[Text Word])

Filters: from 2010 – 2020

Results: 134

Cerebrovascular stroke

We used the following search string:

(((stroke[MeSH Terms]) AND (incidence[MeSH Terms])) AND "Humans"[MeSH]) AND "Stroke/epidemiology"[MAJR] Filters: Meta-Analysis, Review, Systematic Review, from 2010 - 2020

Results: 222

These three articles give the best information about the incidence of cerebrovascular stroke:

- Global stroke statistics. Amanda G Thrift, Tharshanah Thayabaranathan, George Howard, more... (Appendix 1) (20)
- The Epidemiology of Atrial Fibrillation and Stroke. Francesca Pistoia MD, PhD Simona Sacco MD Cindy Tiseo MD Diana Degan MD Raffaele Ornello MD Antonio Carolei MD, FAHA (Appendix 2) (21)

- Global and regional burden of first-ever ischaemic and haemorrhagic stroke during 1990–2010: findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. Rita V Krishnamurthi, PhD, Prof Valery L Feigin, MD, Prof Mohammad H Forouzanfar, MD, George A Mensah, MD, more... (appendix 3) (22)

Haemorrhagic disease

We used the following search string:

(((((("Thrombocytopenia/epidemiology"[MeSH]) AND (incidence[Text Word]) AND (2010:2020[pdat])) NOT (drug induced[Text Word])) NOT (drug induced[Text Word])) NOT (heparin[Text Word])) NOT (cancer[Text Word])) Filters: Meta-Analysis, Review, Systematic Review, Humans, English

Results: 40

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Appendix 1 (20)

Country, study period	Incidence rate per 100,000 population (95% confidence interval)		Standard criteria met ^a
	Men	Women	
Age adjusted to the European standard population			
Belarus (Grodno), 2001–2003 ²⁴	356 (334–377)	236 (222–250)	Yes
Croatia (Varaždin county), 2007–2009 ²⁵	282 (256–309.9)	181.1 (165.6–197.6)	No
France (Dijon), 2000–2006 ³⁴	107.5 (98.3–116.8)	68.9 (62.7–75)	Yes
Italy (Sesto Fiorentino), 2004–2006 ^{73,74}	101.2 (82.5–123)	63 (48.5–80.7)	Yes
Italy (Valle d' Aosta), 2004–2005 ²⁰	159 (127–190)	100 (75–125)	Yes
Kuwait, 1989, 1992, 1993 ⁷⁵	35.48 (35.39–35.56)	16.66 (16.59–16.73)	No
Lithuania (Kaunas), 2004 ⁷⁶	239.3 (209.9–271.6)	158.7 (135–185.4)	Yes
Poland (Warsaw), 2005 ²⁶	140 (132–147)	120 (114–127)	Yes
Spain (Castilla y León, Extremadura, and Comunitat Valenciana regions), 2005 ³⁵	99 (81–117)	66 (53–80)	No
Spain (Menorca), 2004–2006 ^{73,74}	116.3 (96.1–139.5)	65.8 (50.9–83.8)	No
*Spain (La Rioja), 2009 ¹⁶	206 (187.7–224.4)	139.3 (127.0–151.5)	No
United Kingdom (South London), 2004–2006 ²⁸	121.1 (100.5–144.7)	78.1 (61.8–97.5)	Yes
China (Beijing), 2000 ³⁶	147.6 (134.6–162.6)	124 (113–137.4)	No
China (Changsha), 2000 ³⁶	190 (175.2–207.3)	119.1 (108.5–132.3)	No
China (Shanghai), 2000 ³⁶	87.3 (78.5–98.2)	68.1 (61–77.3)	No
France (Dijon), 2000–2006 ³⁴	72.5 (65.9–79.1)	47.3 (45.5–52)	Yes
Iran (Mashhad), 2006–2007 ¹⁸	208 (180–236)	198 (170–226)	Yes
Age adjusted to WHO World standard population			
*Australia (Adelaide), 2009–2010 ¹²	91 (73–112)	61 (47–78)	Yes
Belarus (Grodno), 2001–2003 ²⁴	266 (250–282)	180 (169–191)	Yes
Bulgaria (Rural), 2002 ⁷⁷	909 (729.67–1132.41)	667 (529.24–840.61)	No
Bulgaria (Urban), 2002 ⁷⁷	597 (491.2–725.59)	322 (255.14–406.637)	No
Croatia (Varaždin county), 2007–2009 ²⁵	213.1 (194–233.3)	137.6 (126.3–150.9)	No
India (Trivandrum, rural), 2005 ³¹	163.4 (122.4–204.4)	115.3 (83–147.6)	Yes
India (Trivandrum, urban), 2005 ³¹	141.7 (122.1–161.3)	130.1 (113.3–146.9)	Yes
India (Kolkata), 2003–2005 ⁷⁸	117.1 (87.8–152.6)	178.0 (102.4–223.2)	Yes
Italy (Valle d' Aosta), 2004–2005 ²⁰	122 (94–150)	77 (55–99)	Yes
*Italy (Valle d' Aosta), 2004–2008 ⁷	100 (89–112)	62 (53–71)	Yes
*Japan (Iwate State) ¹⁵	190 (172–209)	104 (91–118)	No
*Martinique (Caribbean) ¹⁴	90 (79–101)	69 (60–78)	Yes
*New Zealand (Auckland) ¹⁰	129 (120–138)	110 (103–119)	Yes
*Spain (La Rioja) ¹⁶	131.0 (119.3–142.6)	86.2 (78.6–93.8)	No

Appendix 2 (21)

Table 1 Crude incidence rates (per 1000) of stroke in population-based studies		
Study Location	Years	Incidence Rate (95% CI)
Oyabe, Japan	1987–1991	4.1 (3.8–4.4)
Frederiksberg, Denmark	1989–1990	3.1 (2.7–3.4)
Espoo-Kauniainen, Finland	1989–1991	2.2 (2.0–2.4)
Auckland, New Zealand	1991–1992	1.4 (1.3–1.5)
Novosibirsk, Russia	1992	2.3 (2.1–2.5)
Belluno, Italy	1992–1993	2.2 (2.0–2.4)
Arcadia, Greece	1993–1995	3.4 (3.1–3.7)
Innhherred, Norway	1994–1996	3.1 (2.8–3.4)
Erlangen, Germany	1994–1998	1.3 (1.2–1.4)
L'Aquila, Italy	1994–1998	2.9 (2.9–3.0)
Perth, Australia	1995–1996	1.6 (1.4–1.8)
South London, UK	1995–1996	1.3 (1.2–1.4)
Melbourne, Australia	1996–1997	2.1 (1.8–2.3)
Martinique, Caribbean	1998–1999	1.6 (1.5–1.8)
Uzhgorod, Ovest Ucraina	1999–2001	2.8 (2.5–3.1)
Perth, Australia	2000–2001	1.2 (1.0–1.4)
Dijon, France	2000–2006	1.1 (1.0–1.2)
Lund-Orup, Sweden	2001–2002	1.9 (1.7–2.1)
Tartu, Estonia	2001–2003	2.2 (2.0–2.4)
Auckland, New Zealand	2002–2003	1.5 (1.5–1.6)
Oxfordshire, UK	2002–2004	1.4 (1.2–1.6)
Valle d'Aosta, Italy	2004–2005	2.2 (2.0–2.5)
Mumbai, India	2005–2006	1.4 (1.3–1.5)
Martinique, Caribbean	2007–2008	1.5 (1.3–1.6)
Kurashiki, Japan	2009–2010	1.6 (1.5–1.7)
Dublin, Ireland	2012	1.7 (1.5–1.8)

Appendix 3 (22)

	1990		2005		2010		p value*
	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	
High-income countries							
Aged <20 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	8268	2.46 (2.25–2.67)	6680	2.21 (2.00–2.43)	6110	2.11 (1.91–2.33)	0.013
MIR	–	0.035 (0.031–0.041)	–	0.031 (0.022–0.037)	–	0.025 (0.017–0.031)	0.006
DALYs	35 027	10.42 (9.49–11.77)	28 444	9.42 (6.92–10.83)	22 912	7.89 (5.68–9.66)	0.008
Mortality	384	0.11 (0.10–0.13)	291	0.10 (0.06–0.11)	223	0.08 (0.05–0.10)	0.003
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	5107	1.52 (1.40–1.65)	3735	1.24 (1.13–1.36)	3393	1.17 (1.07–1.28)	<0.001
MIR	–	0.289 (0.238–0.335)	–	0.196 (0.160–0.232)	–	0.163 (0.127–0.198)	<0.001
DALYs	154 507	45.98 (37.73–51.49)	71 713	23.76 (20.49–26.98)	55 326	19.06 (15.66–22.17)	<0.001
Mortality	1974	0.59 (0.48–0.66)	907	0.30 (0.26–0.34)	691	0.24 (0.19–0.28)	<0.001
Aged ≥20–64 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	619 121	87.16 (81.02–93.66)	663 271	85.60 (79.89–91.93)	743 213	93.82 (87.23–100.81)	0.060
MIR	–	0.142 (0.122–0.157)	–	0.114 (0.098–0.128)	–	0.092 (0.077–0.104)	<0.001
DALYs	2 818 833	396.84 (353.88–423.46)	2 650 292	342.02 (302.66–371.93)	2 451 018	309.40 (272.20–340.16)	<0.001
Mortality	87 833	12.37 (10.74–13.29)	75 345	9.72 (8.37–10.66)	68 140	8.60 (7.31–9.59)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	343 294	48.33 (44.87–52.17)	379 159	48.93 (45.35–52.75)	409 193	51.65 (47.80–55.32)	0.105
MIR	–	0.465 (0.407–0.519)	–	0.368 (0.320–0.413)	–	0.294 (0.255–0.335)	<0.001
DALYs	5 369 589	755.94 (673.55–821.03)	4 878 882	629.62 (560.28–688.56)	4 148 598	523.70 (463.91–581.56)	<0.001
Mortality	159 383	22.44 (19.89–24.48)	139 460	18.00 (15.97–19.81)	119 958	15.14 (13.30–16.94)	<0.001
Aged 65–74 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 013 498	1212.57 (1122.02–1302.50)	1 207 812	1136.70 (1059.80–1220.27)	1 206 882	1104.11 (1027.09–1183.37)	0.031
MIR	–	0.188 (0.159–0.206)	–	0.177 (0.154–0.196)	–	0.143 (0.126–0.158)	<0.001
DALYs	3 781 762	4524.60 (3941.34–4749.17)	4 348 756	4092.73 (3599.19–4348.87)	3 546 196	3244.21 (2906.40–3457.03)	<0.001
Mortality	189 921	227.23 (196.05–239.23)	213 996	201.40 (176.80–214.06)	172 850	158.13 (141.31–169.43)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	237 332	283.95 (261.35–306.24)	268 304	252.51 (233.33–273.71)	273 711	250.40 (232.66–270.48)	0.009
MIR	–	0.574 (0.509–0.652)	–	0.492 (0.432–0.575)	–	0.391 (0.346–0.460)	<0.001
DALYs	2 616 799	3130.80 (2838.73–3459.35)	2 547 071	2397.11 (2191.68–2767.00)	2 056 267	1881.16 (1720.23–2175.44)	<0.001
Mortality	136 046	162.77 (146.94–179.98)	131 703	123.95 (113.39–143.70)	106 836	97.74 (89.22–113.97)	<0.001
Aged ≥75 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 751 254	2824.36 (2627.56–3018.41)	2 031 829	2365.13 (2201.91–2540.09)	2 297 052	2344.00 (2197.01–2503.82)	<0.001
MIR	–	0.537 (0.475–0.584)	–	0.466 (0.428–0.513)	–	0.422 (0.388–0.466)	0.003
DALYs	8 279 171	13 354.53 (11 987.70–13 857.29)	8 273 750	9 660.42 (9 191.97–10 223.96)	8 231 616	8 434.88 (8 041.62–9 048.47)	<0.001
Mortality	939 894	1 511.37 (1 353.61–1 565.14)	946 346	1 082.75 (1 031.81–1 161.73)	968 866	950.10 (905.53–1 030.62)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	2 583 272	4 175.1 (3 859.3–4 507.9)	3 231 137	3 785.4 (3 498.9–4 096.0)	3 646 687	3 801.4 (3 513.7–4 095.8)	0.035
MIR	–	0.979 (0.882–1.118)	–	0.820 (0.731–0.954)	–	0.748 (0.664–0.870)	<0.001
DALYs	2 359 112	3 817.36 (3 571.28–4 300.03)	2 342 929	2 776.87 (2 589.80–3 203.22)	2 309 063	2 457.70 (2 273.57–2 848.71)	<0.001
Mortality	252 454	4 071.0 (3 804.8–4 620.6)	264 630	3 065.4 (2 855.4–3 536.3)	272 324	2 750.6 (2 537.5–3 203.3)	<0.001
All ages							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	3 392 142	193.02 (179.74–205.88)	3 909 592	172.07 (161.23–183.52)	4 253 257	168.45 (158.25–179.52)	0.001
MIR	–	0.359 (0.316–0.390)	–	0.316 (0.290–0.343)	–	0.285 (0.263–0.311)	<0.001
DALYs	14 914 794	842.32 (749.15–875.30)	15 301 242	671.23 (618.65–703.07)	14 251 741	556.98 (517.25–588.11)	<0.001

(Continues on next page)

	1990		2005		2010		p value*
	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	
(Continued from previous page)							
Mortality	1218 033	63.80 (56.45–66.00)	1235 978	47.77 (45.04–50.41)	1210080	40.29 (38.23–43.12)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	844105	53.30 (49.44–57.25)	974 336	49.12 (45.75–52.84)	1050985	48.81 (45.44–52.13)	0.032
MIR	–	0.652 (0.589–0.729)	–	0.551 (0.492–0.628)	–	0.476 (0.430–0.546)	<0.001
DALYs	10500007	695.26 (629.69–753.52)	9 840594	529.78 (484.51–582.25)	8 569 255	425.13 (385.67–470.63)	<0.001
Mortality	549858	32.65 (29.95–35.68)	536 700	24.55 (22.67–27.37)	499 809	20.25 (18.57–22.91)	<0.001
Low-income countries							
Aged <20 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	37 604	1.96 (1.74–2.21)	42 644	1.98 (1.78–2.23)	42 607	1.97 (1.76–2.19)	0.467
MIR	–	0.158 (0.128–0.196)	–	0.108 (0.085–0.132)	–	0.099 (0.078–0.120)	<0.001
DALYs	725 569	37.81 (31.77–44.84)	564 074	26.20 (20.44–31.46)	516 534	23.85 (17.78–28.53)	<0.001
Mortality	8 737	0.46 (0.38–0.54)	6 788	0.32 (0.25–0.38)	6 212	0.29 (0.21–0.34)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	24 132	1.26 (1.12–1.42)	31 290	1.45 (1.31–1.63)	31 333	1.45 (1.30–1.60)	0.036
MIR	–	1.153 (0.858–1.439)	–	0.695 (0.484–0.895)	–	0.638 (0.433–0.832)	<0.001
DALYs	3 842 839	200.23 (148.70–247.29)	2 909 492	135.12 (94.33–166.46)	2 658 426	122.75 (84.26–154.03)	<0.001
Mortality	47 489	2.47 (1.84–3.05)	36 251	1.68 (1.18–2.08)	33 152	1.53 (1.05–1.91)	<0.001
Aged ≥20–64 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 048 665	52.22 (46.05–59.19)	1 605 620	57.20 (50.38–65.30)	1 958 154	62.80 (55.35–71.12)	0.023
MIR	–	0.162 (0.125–0.229)	–	0.131 (0.105–0.176)	–	0.116 (0.096–0.152)	0.001
DALYs	5 724 385	285.06 (235.39–382.78)	7 242 596	258.01 (221.90–331.52)	7 822 374	250.88 (222.65–313.29)	0.013
Mortality	169 222	8.43 (6.79–11.60)	209 449	7.46 (6.28–9.87)	226 360	7.26 (6.36–9.35)	0.006
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	932 934	46.46 (40.34–53.15)	1 699 290	60.54 (52.05–71.01)	2 048 034	65.68 (56.36–76.71)	0.001
MIR	–	0.736 (0.569–0.918)	–	0.494 (0.397–0.602)	–	0.422 (0.333–0.515)	<0.001
DALYs	23 320 724	1161.33 (946.76–1394.12)	2 883 888	1027.33 (877.98–1183.65)	2 945 014	944.51 (802.88–1095.88)	<0.001
Mortality	682 773	34.00 (27.64–41.04)	833 453	29.69 (25.27–34.26)	858 841	27.54 (23.33–32.06)	<0.001
Aged 65–74 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 448 192	1152.07 (993.10–1330.23)	2 242 233	1178.40 (1023.70–1368.17)	2 503 522	1197.93 (1046.63–1376.61)	0.363
MIR	–	0.188 (0.143–0.261)	–	0.167 (0.132–0.222)	–	0.152 (0.125–0.200)	0.039
DALYs	5 256 373	4181.55 (3367.95–5547.71)	7 286 998	3829.67 (3233.25–4924.07)	7 455 071	3567.24 (3120.81–4518.74)	0.005
Mortality	270 306	215.03 (171.34–289.19)	372 174	195.60 (163.42–253.47)	379 837	181.75 (157.63–232.97)	0.006
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	635 720	505.73 (426.21–595.26)	1 138 008	598.08 (507.06–706.31)	1 243 472	595.00 (507.58–703.97)	0.085
MIR	–	0.868 (0.648–1.106)	–	0.632 (0.498–0.791)	–	0.563 (0.434–0.700)	<0.001
DALYs	10 345 455	8230.02 (6557.97–10024.44)	13 489 314	7089.29 (5966.41–8334.24)	13 110 681	6273.45 (5331.21–7356.20)	<0.001
Mortality	547 366	435.44 (345.66–530.97)	714 434	375.47 (315.28–442.45)	695 399	332.75 (282.67–390.97)	<0.001
Aged ≥75 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 312 155	2367.54 (2026.74–2735.51)	2 297 208	2537.52 (2202.95–2941.36)	2 811 999	2575.40 (2240.67–2950.24)	0.222
MIR	–	0.440 (0.355–0.562)	–	0.384 (0.312–0.480)	–	0.362 (0.298–0.443)	0.046
DALYs	5 507 099	9938.45 (8486.20–12399.96)	8 176 998	9013.12 (7860.57–10865.64)	9 343 686	8553.44 (7572.78–10099.22)	0.001
Mortality	574 779	1075.73 (915.74–1336.49)	877 484	997.48 (870.23–1204.49)	1 012 930	949.88 (838.56–1128.36)	0.01
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	403 286	713.83 (603.31–847.38)	793 903	861.85 (735.11–1020.98)	951 173	859.36 (729.17–1012.58)	0.065
MIR	–	1.479 (1.090–1.900)	–	1.094 (0.855–1.356)	–	1.008 (0.784–1.250)	0.002

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	1990		2005		2010		p value*
	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	
(Continued from previous page)							
DALYs	5 873 138	10 249 10 (7846 57-12 615 18)	8 302 502	890 791 (7406 47-10 533 99)	9 054 390	8 113 74 (6818 88-9519 69)	0 002
Mortality	591 886	1072 90 (819 30-1329 49)	862 258	955 71 (789 22-1138 04)	951 562	874 84 (736 84-1026 62)	0 007
Allages							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	3 846 616	170 53 (148 24-195 28)	6 187 705	178 68 (156 28-205 59)	7 316 281	181 70 (159 10-206 78)	0 267
MIR	..	0 266 (0 213-0 354)	..	0 238 (0 193-0 303)	..	0 223 (0 186-0 276)	0 051
DALYs	17213 426	734 86 (619 49-948 36)	23 270 664	658 32 (571 81-818 09)	25 137 666	613 93 (550 41-748 03)	<0 001
Mortality	1 023 044	50 13 (42 02-64 07)	1 465 895	45 77 (39 69-56 27)	1 625 339	43 05 (38 25-51 96)	<0 001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	1996 072	81 40 (69 54-94 31)	3 662 492	98 80 (84 77-115 66)	4 274 013	99 43 (85 37-116 28)	0 040
MIR	..	0 932 (0 708-1 177)	..	0 668 (0 534-0 822)	..	0 595 (0 470-0 729)	<0 001
DALYs	43 382 156	1614 23 (1292 98-1946 36)	53 539 196	1363 83 (1154 83-1580 73)	54 273 644	1207 21 (1024 82-1408 04)	<0 001
Mortality	1 869 514	80 37 (63 72-96 98)	2 446 397	69 29 (58 11-81 26)	2 538 954	61 93 (52 53-72 34)	<0 001
Globally							
Aged <20 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	45 872	2 03 (1 85-2 25)	49 324	2 01 (1 83-2 23)	48 716	1 98 (1 80-2 18)	0 371
MIR	..	0 136 (0 112-0 165)	..	0 098 (0 077-0 118)	..	0 090 (0 070-0 108)	<0 001
DALYs	760 596	33 73 (28 57-39 77)	592 518	24 13 (18 80-28 77)	539 446	21 96 (16 39-26 10)	<0 001
Mortality	9121	0 40 (0 34-0 48)	7079	0 29 (0 22-0 34)	6435	0 26 (0 20-0 31)	<0 001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	29 240	1 30 (1 17-1 43)	35 025	1 43 (1 29-1 58)	34 727	1 41 (1 29-1 56)	0 120
MIR	..	1 001 (0 765-1 237)	..	0 642 (0 452-0 819)	..	0 592 (0 404-0 762)	<0 001
DALYs	3 997 346	177 24 (132 48-217 62)	2 981 205	121 43 (85 31-149 09)	2 713 752	110 50 (76 32-138 09)	<0 001
Mortality	494 64	2 19 (1 64-2 68)	371 59	1 51 (1 07-1 86)	33 843	1 38 (0 95-1 72)	<0 001
Aged ≥20-64 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	1 667 786	61 35 (56 39-66 65)	2 268 891	63 34 (57 92-69 84)	2 701 367	69 09 (63 00-76 01)	0 035
MIR	..	0 154 (0 133-0 194)	..	0 126 (0 108-0 159)	..	0 109 (0 095-0 134)	<0 001
DALYs	8543 219	314 27 (278 37-384 70)	9 892 888	276 19 (249 70-334 81)	10 273 392	262 73 (241 48-312 86)	<0 001
Mortality	257 056	9 46 (8 30-11 77)	284 793	7 95 (7 09-9 86)	294 500	7 53 (6 85-9 24)	<0 001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	1 276 228	46 95 (42 30-51 87)	2 078 450	58 03 (51 33-66 39)	2 457 227	62 84 (55 30-71 67)	0 001
MIR	..	0 662 (0 544-0 787)	..	0 470 (0 389-0 557)	..	0 400 (0 325-0 478)	<0 001
DALYs	28 690 314	1055 41 (895 45-1232 70)	33 716 770	941 29 (818 42-1072 58)	33 598 744	859 26 (741 90-985 04)	<0 001
Mortality	842 156	30 98 (26 27-36 36)	972 913	27 16 (23 57-31 04)	978 799	25 03 (21 57-28 77)	<0 001
Aged 65-74 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	2 461 690	1176 23 (1073 89-1291 17)	3 450 045	1163 46 (1053 37-1287 36)	3 710 404	1165 71 (1057 96-1284 45)	0 426
MIR	..	0 187 (0 161-0 229)	..	0 170 (0 147-0 205)	..	0 149 (0 130-0 180)	0 001
DALYs	9 038 136	4318 55 (3864 39-5068 30)	11 635 754	3923 93 (3559 88-4600 94)	11 001 267	3456 31 (3184 54-4085 80)	<0 001
Mortality	460 226	219 90 (195 49-261 22)	586 170	197 67 (178 67-234 07)	552 687	173 64 (158 88-207 65)	<0 001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	873 052	417 16 (369 14-471 98)	1 406 313	474 25 (414 57-545 31)	1 517 183	476 66 (418 82-549 38)	0 078
MIR	..	0 786 (0 627-0 967)	..	0 605 (0 491-0 730)	..	0 531 (0 426-0 640)	<0 001
DALYs	12 962 254	6193 55 (5168 67-7330 20)	16 036 385	5407 96 (4672 18-6260 19)	15 166 948	4765 06 (4129 38-5527 14)	<0 001
Mortality	683 412	326 54 (272 05-386 99)	846 138	285 34 (245 88-331 99)	802 234	252 04 (218 06-292 88)	<0 001
Aged ≥75 years							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	3 063 410	2614 89 (2426 49-2809 55)	4 329 037	2452 72 (2245 04-2674 44)	5 109 051	2472 93 (2279 15-2687 39)	0 176

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	1990		2005		2010		p value*
	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	n	Point estimate (95% CI)	
(Continued from previous page)							
MIR	..	0.495 (0.450-0.547)		0.422 (0.379-0.483)		0.389 (0.348-0.450)	<0.001
DALYs	13786270	11766.13 (11034.98-12688.85)	16450747	9314.39 (8699.15-10498.56)	17575302	8509.08 (7979.52-9562.85)	<0.001
Mortality	1514673	1313.55 (1225.05-1407.29)	1823831	1040.14 (972.42-1184.36)	1981797	952.73 (893.26-1082.61)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	661658	558.61 (503.36-624.07)	1117040	630.25 (558.49-712.17)	1315860	640.06 (569.10-724.72)	0.046
MIR	..	1.280 (1.041-1.542)		1.012 (0.841-1.208)		0.934 (0.767-1.107)	0.001
DALYs	8232250	6899.22 (5819.05-8101.89)	10645431	5985.97 (5185.38-6900.83)	11363453	5544.55 (4848.87-6377.47)	<0.001
Mortality	844340	719.66 (605.91-844.83)	1126888	638.52 (554.36-736.04)	1223886	592.56 (517.87-681.36)	<0.001
All ages							
Ischaemic							
Incidence	7238758	181.19 (167.30-196.23)	10097297	175.46 (160.08-192.26)	11569538	176.44 (161.46-192.21)	0.324
MIR	..	0.310 (0.278-0.352)		0.268 (0.237-0.310)		0.245 (0.219-0.285)	<0.001
DALYs	32128220	795.80 (733.54-906.40)	38571908	667.77 (617.11-774.20)	39389408	597.80 (559.75-691.68)	<0.001
Mortality	2241077	57.59 (53.69-63.97)	2701873	46.92 (43.58-53.67)	2835419	42.27 (39.60-48.71)	<0.001
Haemorrhagic							
Incidence	2840177	69.36 (62.46-77.18)	4636828	80.33 (71.40-91.69)	5324997	81.52 (72.27-92.82)	0.033
MIR	..	0.847 (0.692-1.009)		0.643 (0.536-0.766)		0.571 (0.471-0.676)	<0.001
DALYs	53882164	1266.94 (1068.41-1484.26)	63379792	1081.81 (935.41-1234.23)	62842896	956.22 (827.57-1104.44)	<0.001
Mortality	2419372	59.66 (50.61-69.71)	2983097	51.61 (44.68-59.07)	3038763	46.14 (40.13-53.15)	<0.001

Data are point estimates (95% CIs), unless otherwise indicated. DALYs=disability-adjusted life-years. *p-values are for the trend in rates between 1990 and 2010 only.

Table 3: Age-adjusted annual incidence and mortality rates (per 100 000 person-years), mortality-to-incidence ratio (MIR), and DALYs lost for ischaemic and haemorrhagic stroke, by age group in high-income, low-income, and middle-income countries, and globally in 1990, 2005, and 2010